

1 **Ecological consequences of artificial light at night on coastal species in**
2 **natural and artificial habitats – A review**

3 Ferretti M. ^{1*} 0009-0006-6819-3584, Rossi F. ² 0000-0003-1928-9193, Benedetti Cecchi L. ¹ 0000-
4 0001-5244-5202, Maggi E. ¹ 0000-0001-6934-9380

5 ¹Dipartimento di Biologia, Università di Pisa, CoNISMa, via Derna 1, 56126 Pisa, Italy.

6 ²Genova Marine Center, Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn - National Institute of Marine Biology,
7 Ecology and Biotechnology, Villa del Principe, Piazza del Principe 4, 16126 Genoa, Italy

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9 *corresponding author: miriam.ferretti@phd.unipi.it

10

11 **Abstract**

12 The urbanisation of coastal areas increases both Artificial Light At Night (ALAN) and man-made
13 structures. ALAN poses significant challenges to coastal ecosystems by altering species physiology
14 and behaviour. Its effects might differ considerably between man-made and natural habitats due to
15 varying habitat complexity and biological assemblages. This systematic review assesses the current
16 knowledge and gaps regarding the ecological effects of the interaction between ALAN and different
17 coastal hard-bottom habitats on intertidal and shallow-subtidal reefs. Of the 57 retrieved studies,
18 most are laboratory experiments (40) on the physiology and behaviour of rocky shore (24) or coral
19 reef (16) species. Field studies were conducted in artificial (6) and natural habitats (9), with only 2
20 comparing the two habitat types. These studies illustrate ALAN impacts on various species, with
21 potential cascading effects on entire communities through the alteration of competitive and
22 consumer-resource interactions. Different habitat structures may interact with ALAN by generating
23 highly heterogeneous lightscapes (e.g., natural rocky shores), regular light-shadow mosaics (e.g.,
24 breakwaters), vast homogeneously lit areas (e.g., seawalls), or constantly shaded areas (e.g.,
25 pontoons). This creates a variable mismatch in natural light conditions, which may be further
26 influenced by the introduction of additional light sources (e.g., moored boats with underwater
27 coloured lights). As coastal development and light pollution continue to grow, research should
28 prioritise understanding their interactive effects in shaping species relationships and ecosystem
29 dynamics. Although the available evidence suggests that ALAN effects may vary between natural
30 and man-made habitats, further research is needed to draw any general conclusion.

31 **Keywords:** artificial structures, coastal development, light pollution, ALAN, hard-bottom habitats,
32 rocky shores

33 **Introduction**

34 Artificial Light At Night (ALAN) is an emergent but globally widespread stressor that is changing
35 the natural brightness and spectral composition of night skies (Davies and Smyth 2018; Jechow et
36 al. 2020; Gaston et al. 2021). More than 22% of the world's coastline is currently exposed to
37 ALAN, mostly due to permanent sources of light such as street lamps used in towns and ports for
38 recreational activities or safety purposes (Davies et al. 2014; Žák and Vondráčková 2016;
39 Cianchetti-Benedetti et al. 2018). This results in ALAN intensity ranging from 0.1 to 22 lux at the
40 sea surface (Gaston et al. 2013; Davies et al. 2015). By penetrating shallow coastal waters, light
41 pollution affects 1.9 million km² of seas at 1-metre depth. However, its impact is still notable at 10-
42 metre depth and can even extend to 20-metre depth under clear water conditions (Smyth et al.
43 2022).

44 The capability to perceive light enables organisms to regulate their activities in time (daily, lunar
45 or seasonal rhythms of physiology and behaviours) and in space (phototropism or phototaxy)
46 (Davies and Smyth 2018; Tidau et al. 2021). By disrupting the natural light-dark cycles, ALAN
47 impacts a wide range of marine species that have adapted to these patterns over millennia (Bulla et
48 al. 2017). For instance, ALAN has been shown to disrupt circadian rhythms in marine species by
49 altering their behaviour, physiology, and gene expression (Marangoni et al. 2022; Stanton and
50 Cowart 2024). The expanding application of light-emitting diodes (LEDs) poses an additional
51 threat, due to the dominance of short wavelengths (blue light radiation), which can penetrate deeper
52 waters than other light sources, thus affecting a wider range of aquatic habitats and species (Davies
53 et al. 2014).

54 ALAN is tightly associated with urban development and the resulting spread of man-made
55 structures along shorelines (Komyakova et al. 2022). Nowadays, over two-thirds of world
56 megacities (i.e., cities with over 10 million inhabitants) are built in low-elevation coastal bands and
57 2.15 billion people live within 100 km away from the coast (Smyth et al. 2022; Reimann et al.
58 2023). Coastal man-made structures add novel habitats in areas dominated by soft sediments or
59 replace natural hard-bottom shores with substrates of different physical structure (Connell 2000;
60 Davis et al. 2002; Bulleri and Chapman 2004). In some cases, artificial structures can introduce
61 unique habitat features that have no equivalent in natural environments. For example, vertical
62 seawalls provide a steep, flat habitat with low topographic complexity. These grey infrastructures
63 are usually made of material with low roughness (basalt or concrete with 0.20 mm and 0.13 mm
64 roughness respectively; Leroux 2014; Cacabelos et al. 2016), thus decreasing the substrate
65 microtopography (millimetre to centimetre scale). In contrast, breakwaters provide complex habitats
66 with high modularity, characterised by the repetition in space of patterns of different structural

67 components. A peculiar condition may be created by jetties and docks, which provide shading at
68 scales of tens to hundreds of metres, during the day under natural light (Pardal-Souza et al. 2016).

69 Assemblages may differ considerably between natural and artificial substrates and have different
70 levels of diversity and susceptibility to disturbance (Henseler et al. 2019), including ALAN.

71 Moreover, habitat complexity might modulate how light reaches the shore, thus interacting with
72 ALAN and how it affects natural and artificial habitats, as recently suggested by Trethewy et al.
73 (2023). Based on these preliminary observations, we, therefore, postulate that the structural
74 complexity (*sensu* Bulleri and Chapman 2010; i.e., the number of different components like pits,
75 cracks, crevices, etc.), as well as the roughness and surface inclination of man-made versus natural
76 habitat, should be considered when dealing with ALAN effects in coastal areas.

77 Based on a systematic review of the scientific literature, we first discuss current knowledge on
78 ALAN effects in natural and artificial hard-bottom habitats (either intertidal or shallow subtidal).
79 The identified studies are categorised as either field or laboratory-based; field studies are further
80 divided between those conducted in natural or artificial habitats, with particular attention to research
81 comparing ALAN effects across these habitat types. We then address gaps in knowledge by
82 focusing on potential mechanisms of interactions of ALAN with the presence (and extent) of
83 different coastal artificial structures.

84 **Methodology for the systematic literature search**

85 A comprehensive literature search was conducted to identify studies examining ALAN impacts in
86 intertidal and shallow subtidal (tens of metres deep) marine coastal habitats. The literature search
87 followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA)
88 guidelines (Page et al. 2021).

89 In May 2024, we launched the search on two major publication databases, Web of Science and
90 Scopus, employing the following search string:

91 ("city light*" OR "unnatural light*" OR "artificial light* at night" OR "nighttime light*" OR
92 "night-time light*" OR "light* pollution" OR "artificial light*" OR "outdoor light*" OR "night sky
93 pollution" OR "global light emission*" OR "artificially lit" OR "street light*" OR "artificial
94 illumination*" OR "artificial *glow" OR "anthropogenic light*" OR "light* at night" OR "ALAN")
95 AND (*shore* OR intertidal OR subtidal OR sea OR coast* OR reef* OR sand* OR rock* OR
96 estuar* OR saltmarsh OR salt-marsh OR "salt marsh" OR "marine *structure*" OR "artificial
97 structure*" OR marin* OR bay OR lagoon OR mud* OR mangrove* OR port*).

98 Papers were evaluated for inclusion according to a three-level process (Fig. 1; Supplementary
99 material).

100 **ALAN impacts on different hard-bottom habitat types**

101 The systematic literature search identified 57 studies conducted in hard-bottom habitats or on
102 species associated with them (Table S1). Most studies (40) were carried out in the laboratory,
103 involving species collected from natural rocky shores (17) and coral reefs (11), or supplied by
104 aquaculture facilities (12). Field studies (17) were conducted on natural rocky shores (6), coral reefs
105 (3) and different types of artificial habitats (6), with only 2 studies investigating the interaction
106 between ALAN and habitat types by comparing artificial and natural environments.

107 **Laboratory studies**

108 Laboratory studies have mainly focused on the behavioural and physiological mechanisms in
109 response to artificial lighting, including the molecular aspects regulating them.

110 ALAN frequently affects species movement, but results vary among species and life stages. For
111 example, ALAN increases the swimming activity of adult rockfish (*Girella laevisformis*) but it
112 disorients juveniles (Pulgar et al. 2019, 2023). Some species, such as grey mullets (*Mugil cephalus*)
113 are attracted by specific light colours (violet and blue lights; Marchesan et al. 2005). Other species
114 decrease their movement or increase their righting time, often used as an indicator of stress (e.g.,
115 abalones *Haliotis discus hannai* and *Concholepas concholepas* and sea urchin *Heliocidaris*
116 *crassispina*; Manríquez et al. 2019; Xu et al. 2023; Zhang et al. 2024), while lobsters show no
117 changes in locomotion (*Panulirus argus*; Steell et al. 2020). Some invertebrates, including those
118 mentioned above (*C. concholepas*, *H. crassispina*), and the isopode *Ligia oceanica* also change
119 their predator-avoidance behaviour (Manríquez et al. 2019, 2021a; Bullough et al. 2023; Xu et al.
120 2023). As for predator-prey interactions, ALAN can even increase camouflage efficiency in
121 Littorinidae species (Moyses et al. 2023).

122 Some invertebrates modify their foraging behaviour under ALAN conditions. Species like the sea
123 urchins *Centrostephanus rodgersii* and *Paracentrotus lividus*, and the dogwhelk *Nucella lapillus*,
124 reverse lunar-guided foraging patterns and/or increase grazing intensity (Underwood et al. 2017;
125 Bauer et al. 2022; Tidau et al. 2022; Caley et al. 2024). In filter feeders, exposure to certain colours
126 either decreases feeding activity (e.g., the blue mussels *Mytilus edulis* exposed to red or white light)
127 or increases gaping frequency without increasing food intake (e.g., mussels under green light, and
128 the Pacific oyster *Crassostrea gigas* under red, green or blue light; Botté et al. 2023a; Christoforou
129 et al. 2023). The anemone *Metridium senile* reduces tentacle expansion and alters circadian feeding
130 rhythms (Lynn et al. 2024), while diurnal corals increase tentacle expansion at increasing ALAN
131 intensities (e.g., *Stylophora pistillata* and *Duncanopsamma axiefuga* exposed to 10-35 lux;
132 Mardones et al. 2023). Some studies have shown that a temporally limited exposure to ALAN (from

133 sunset to midnight) reduces impacts on the feeding behaviour of oysters, sea urchins and gastropods
134 (Bauer et al. 2022; Botté et al. 2023b).

135 At the molecular level, ALAN can affect the expression of genes regulating rhythms in physiology
136 and behaviour, such as the molecular clock in *Crassostrea gigas* (Botté et al. 2023c),
137 photosensitivity in the sea urchin *H. crassispina*, in the surgeon *A. triostegus* and abalones (Fogg et
138 al. 2023; Zhang et al. 2023; Xu et al. 2024). ALAN may also affect the synthesis of proteins
139 essential to embryonic growth and adaptation to light conditions (Gao et al. 2024) and cell
140 proliferation (as in *Acropora eurystoma*; Rosenberg et al. 2019). Altered levels of proteins
141 (including enzymes) and metabolites have been observed in sea anemones, abalone larvae and coral
142 reef fish under ALAN conditions (Hillyer et al. 2021; Lynn et al. 2024; Zhang et al. 2024).

143 ALAN can also affect physiological responses, ultimately affecting reproduction and growth in a
144 variety of organisms. For example, studies have shown that exposure to ALAN interferes with
145 gamete release decreasing fertilization and hatching success in the corals *Acropora millepora* and
146 *Acropora digitifera* (Kaniewska et al. 2015; Ayalon et al. 2021b) and in the clownfish *Amphiprion*
147 *ocellaris* (Fobert et al. 2019, 2021). In contrast, ALAN has positive effects on the sea urchins *H.*
148 *crassispina* and *C. rodgersii* by increasing their gonadic index (Caley et al. 2023; Xu et al. 2023).

149 Physiological impacts of ALAN may reverberate on the growth rate and survival of organisms, as
150 observed in various invertebrates such as snails (*H. discus hannai*), sea urchins (*H. crassispina*),
151 mussels (*Mytilus edulis*), and barnacles (*Austrominius modestus*; Tidau et al. 2023; Xu et al. 2023;
152 Zhang et al. 2023). Similar effects are observed in corals, likely due to changes in the
153 photosynthetic activity of their microbial community (e.g., *S. pistillata* and *Acropora cervicornis*;
154 Ayalon et al. 2019, 2021a, 2024; Baquiran et al. 2020; Levy et al. 2020; Tamir et al. 2020; Slagel et
155 al. 2021; Kramer et al. 2023). Contrasting effects are observed in fishes: the dark-banded rockfish,
156 *Sebastes inermis*, exhibits higher growth rates (Yoon et al. 2008), while the convict surgeon,
157 *Acanthurus triostegus*, experiences higher mortality rates (O'Connor et al. 2019).

158 **Field studies**

159 The few field studies conducted on natural rocky shores (6) show various effects at the individual
160 level, such as the reduction of the camouflage efficiency of gastropods, the impairment of the
161 settlement behaviour in different benthic invertebrates and the rhythmicity of circadian gene
162 expressions in marine plants (Manríquez et al. 2021b; McMahon et al. 2022; Dalle Carbonare et al.
163 2023). Some of these studies revealed impacts at the community level. During short-term ALAN
164 exposure (1 month), increased grazing pressure by *Melarhaphé neritoides* compensated for the rise
165 in autotroph biomass and photosynthetic efficiency (Maggi and Benedetti-Cecchi 2018). However,

166 with prolonged exposure time (3 months), ALAN significantly reduced the density of grazers (thus
167 erasing their effects on heterotrophic bacteria), while increasing the diversity of cyanobacterial
168 families (Maggi et al. 2020a, 2020b).

169 A relatively large spectrum of effects has been observed also in the few field studies (3) conducted
170 in coral reefs. ALAN advances the timing of mass spawning in different coral genera at various
171 locations (e.g., *Acropora* spp., *Montipora* spp. in the Red Sea, China Sea and Persian Gulf), reduces
172 growth and survival rates in the juvenile anemonefish *Amphiprion chrysopterus* and alters the
173 camouflage behaviour in the diurnal coral reef fish *Dascyllus aruanus* (Schligler et al. 2021; Davies
174 et al. 2023; Georgiou et al. 2024).

175 Among the 6 studies on light pollution conducted in artificial habitats, there is one of the earliest
176 published papers on ALAN (Weiss 1947), which revealed an increased early-settlement rate of
177 larvae of the barnacle *Balanus improvisus* at night under an artificially illuminated boat slip,
178 compared to natural nighttime conditions. Later, two papers revealed variable effects on different
179 settlement stages in sessile invertebrates, colonising both vertical walls of a wooden wharf (e.g., the
180 acorn barnacle *Semibalanus balanoides*; Lynn et al. 2021) and PVC plates on a floating raft (Davies
181 et al. 2015).

182 The presence of artificial light on man-made structures appears to increase the abundance of
183 specific size classes of fishes, i.e., large predators (>500 mm length) and small shoaling fishes
184 (<100 mm length), as reported near a floating restaurant (Becker et al. 2013); or to lead to massive
185 shoal formation in shaded areas of ports and marinas (Mavraki et al. 2016). In addition, Bolton et al.
186 (2017) found that, although ALAN decreases fish abundance under a wharf, it increases predatory
187 behaviour and foraging time, thereby affecting invertebrate assemblages through top-down control.

188 Direct comparisons among different hard-bottom habitat types are currently very limited, with two
189 exceptions. Georgiadis et al. (2014) show that the appearance of the bogue fish (*Boops boops*)
190 shoals during nighttime is exclusive to artificial locations, probably because the shaded areas
191 created by the interaction of ALAN with man-made structures (e.g., piers) may provide shelters,
192 allowing fishes to avoid predation while resting in shallow littoral zones (Georgiadis et al. 2014).
193 Trethewy et al. (2023) observed that under ALAN exposure algal cover increases and grazing
194 gastropod abundance decreases in natural habitats, but an opposite pattern occurs on seawalls. The
195 authors suggested that the inclination of the substrate drives these patterns, by modifying incident
196 light reaching the
197 surface.

198 **Ecological implications of ALAN on natural and man-made hard-bottom** 199 **habitats**

200 Understanding how marine coastal communities respond to ALAN by modifying direct and indirect
201 biological interactions is essential for maintaining ecosystem functions and preserving their health
202 and sustainability. The few studies (6) dealing with multiple taxa on hard-bottom habitats suggest
203 that ALAN impacts on single organisms can indirectly affect entire communities through consumer-
204 resource interactions in both natural (Maggi and Benedetti-Cecchi 2018; Maggi et al. 2020a, 2020b;
205 Moyses et al. 2023) and man-made habitats (Bolton et al. 2017; Trethewy et al. 2023). At the same
206 time, contrasting effects of ALAN in natural versus artificial substrates (Trethewy et al. 2023)
207 assume particular relevance under the increasing presence of a variety of man-made structures
208 worldwide (Bulleri and Chapman 2010; Momota and Hosokawa 2021), often associated with
209 nocturnal artificial lighting.

210 Based on the ecological knowledge of coastal hard-bottom habitats, and ALAN effects observed
211 so far, we highlight some key aspects that, in our opinion, should deserve particular attention for the
212 management of light pollution in these coastal systems.

213 The physical characteristics of man-made versus natural habitats, such as their structural
214 complexity, surface roughness and inclination, as suggested by Trethewy et al. (2023), can
215 significantly modulate the intensity and spatial patterns of artificial light reaching the sea bottom
216 (Fig. 2). The resulting habitat-specific light and shadow mosaics may indeed interact differently
217 with species' light perception capability, physiology and behaviour.

218 The interaction between ALAN and steep vertical structures, like seawalls, can generate nearly
219 homogenous lit areas in terms of angle of incidence and intensity of light beam (Fig. 2a). These
220 concrete structures may provide little to no shading for organisms at small spatial scales
221 (millimetres to centimetres), thus lacking sheltering opportunities for species known to generally
222 prefer complex microhabitats, such as juvenile marine snails or adult littorinid species (Gosselin
223 and Chia 1995; Chapman 2003; Cacabelos et al. 2016). Under ALAN conditions, we expect these
224 organisms to experience higher exposure to light at night. The consequent increased physiological
225 stress and/or visibility could result in greater vulnerability to predators than on natural rocky shores.

226 Moreover, tidal dynamics can significantly modulate the in-water attenuation of ALAN at a given
227 location, as a water column of variable depth will change the intensity, spectral composition and
228 propagation of ALAN reaching the sea bottom (Smyth et al. 2022). It is reasonable to expect this
229 mechanism to be more evident in steep and homogenous habitats (e.g., seawalls) than in more
230 heterogenous artificial or natural substrates.

231 In contrast, when exposed to ALAN, the high modularity structure of riprap breakwaters can
232 create regularly repeating patterns of light and shadows (Fig. 2c). Based on known behaviours
233 under natural conditions (e.g., crabs, large decapods, or fish; Wehkamp and Fischer 2013; Bateman
234 and Fleming 2015), we expect that these structures may offer more opportunities than natural shores
235 for species to seek dark refugia from predators (e.g., birds), or to use this physical complexity to
236 hide and prey, while also taking advantage of their improved visual perception under ALAN
237 conditions.

238 The peculiar shading effect generated by jetties and docks during the day can extend into the night
239 through their interaction with artificial light sources (Becker et al. 2013; Bolton et al. 2017;
240 Mavraki et al. 2016), thereby possibly mitigating ALAN impact, while creating a mismatch in
241 circadian light conditions. We highlight that this mismatch may be further influenced by
242 occasionally moored boats, which can increase the size of shaded areas, or exacerbate the effects of
243 light pollution at night (Fig. 2b). In fact, the presence of moored boats equipped with underwater
244 coloured LED lights (e.g., blue, violet, red) may create a light mosaic of different spectra.

245 Differences in ALAN effects between natural and man-made structures might involve both
246 positive and negative species interactions. Positive interactions play a central role in the functioning
247 of marine coastal systems (Bulleri 2009) and we expect that facilitation might be crucial in
248 regulating the effects of light pollution in intertidal and shallow subtidal habitats. A plethora of
249 sessile and mobile invertebrates use canopy-forming seaweeds as habitat and food (Benedetti-
250 Cecchi et al. 2019), while also taking advantage of sheltering and shading. Shading may be key
251 under ALAN conditions, but no information is available on the magnitude and direction of light
252 pollution effects on canopy-forming seaweeds. These species are known to be susceptible to urban
253 stressors, including the presence of man-made structures (Airoldi and Beck 2007). Therefore, they
254 are more common and diverse on natural rocky shores than artificial structures (Chapman 2003;
255 Mayer-Pinto et al. 2018). Where present, we might expect a gradient of indirect impacts on the
256 understory assemblage – ranging from the loss of facilitative relationships if the canopy is
257 negatively affected by ALAN, to full protection from light at night granted by the presence of
258 macroalgae if ALAN has neutral or positive effects on the seaweed.

259 Although canopy-forming species are typically more common on natural rocky shores, artificial
260 structures are particularly vulnerable to biological invasion, as they are often deployed in areas
261 associated with activities linked to the introduction of non-native species, such as shipping and
262 aquaculture (Vaselli et al. 2008; Bulleri and Chapman 2010). ALAN conditions might exacerbate
263 negative effects of invasive species on resident assemblages. For example, in the Mediterranean Sea
264 the invasive macroalga *Caulerpa racemosa* is known for its morphological plasticity to varying

265 light environments (Klein and Verlaque 2008), and we can expect a more efficient adaptation to
266 extreme ALAN conditions than for native macroalgae.

267 **Conclusions**

268 The accelerating urban development of coastal areas has introduced significant changes to marine
269 coastal ecosystems, including the increase in artificial structures and areas affected by light
270 pollution. We highlighted several key findings and implications regarding the potential differences
271 in ALAN effects on diverse hard-bottom coastal habitats (both natural and artificial). Their
272 structural differences may influence the distribution, intensity and quality of ALAN, leading to
273 diversified ecological responses among marine organisms, which can cascade through trophic levels
274 and affect ecosystem functions. Direct comparisons among different hard-bottom habitat types are
275 still limited, with notable exceptions highlighting unique responses in natural versus artificial
276 structures. These differences highlight the importance of habitat-specific studies to fully understand
277 ecological consequences of light pollution and to preserve the health and sustainability of coastal
278 marine ecosystems undergoing urbanisation.

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290 **Declarations**

291 **Competing interests** The authors declare no financial or non-financial conflict of interest.

292 **Ethical standards** Not applicable.

293 **Consent to participate** Not applicable.

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295 **References**

- 296 Airoldi L, Beck M (2007) Loss, status and trends for coastal marine habitats of Europe. In: Gibson
297 RN, Atkinson RJA, Gordon JDM (ed) *Oceanography and Marine Biology: An annual*
298 *review*, 1st edn. CRC press, 45:345–405.
- 299 Ayalon I, De Barros Marangoni LF, Benichou JIC, Avisar D, Levy O (2019) Red Sea corals under
300 Artificial Light Pollution at Night (ALAN) undergo oxidative stress and photosynthetic
301 impairment. *Glob Change Biol* 25:4194–4207. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14795>
- 302 Ayalon I, Benichou JIC, Avisar D, Levy O (2021a) The endosymbiotic coral algae symbiodiniaceae
303 are sensitive to a sensory pollutant: Artificial Light at Night, ALAN. *Front Physiol*
304 12:695083. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2021.695083>
- 305 Ayalon I, Rosenberg Y, Benichou JIC, Campos CLD, Sayco SLG, Nada MAL, Baquiran JIP,
306 Ligson CA, Avisar D, Conaco C, Kuechly HU, Kyba CCM, Cabaitan PC, Levy O (2021b)
307 Coral gametogenesis collapse under artificial light pollution. *Curr Biol* 31:413-419.e3.
308 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2020.10.039>
- 309 Ayalon I, Avisar D, Jechow A, Levy O (2024) Corals nitrogen and carbon isotopic signatures alters
310 under Artificial Light at Night (ALAN). *Sci Total Environ* 920:170513.
311 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.170513>
- 312 Baquiran JIP, Nada MAL, Campos CLD, Sayco SLG, Cabaitan PC, Rosenberg Y, Ayalon I, Levy
313 O, Conaco C (2020) The prokaryotic microbiome of *Acropora digitifera* is stable under
314 short-term artificial light pollution. *Microorganisms* 8:1566.
315 <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8101566>
- 316 Bateman PW, Fleming PA (2015) Escape behaviour in shore crabs: constraints of body size and
317 available shelter. *J Zool* 297:265–269. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jzo.12276>
- 318 Bauer F, Ritter M, Šiljeg A, Gretschel G, Lenz M (2022) Effects of artificial light at night on the
319 feeding behaviour of three marine benthic grazers from the Adriatic Sea are species-specific
320 and mostly short-lived. *Mar Pollut Bull* 185:114303.
321 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2022.114303>
- 322 Becker A, Whitfield AK, Cowley PD, Järnegren J, Næsje TF (2013) Potential effects of artificial
323 light associated with anthropogenic infrastructure on the abundance and foraging behaviour

- 324 of estuary-associated fishes. *J Appl Ecol* 50:43–50. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365->
325 2664.12024
- 326 Benedetti-Cecchi L, Airoidi L, Bulleri F, Fraschetti S, Terlizzi A (2019) Species interactions and
327 regime shifts in intertidal and subtidal rocky reefs of the Mediterranean Sea. In: Hawkins SJ,
328 Bohn K, Firth LB, Williams GA (eds) *Interactions in the Marine Benthos*, 1st edn.
329 Cambridge University Press, pp 190–213. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108235792.009>
- 330 Bolton D, Mayer-Pinto M, Clark GF, Dafforn KA, Brassil WA, Becker A, Johnston EL (2017)
331 Coastal urban lighting has ecological consequences for multiple trophic levels under the sea.
332 *Sci Total Environ* 576:1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.10.037>
- 333 Botté A, Payton L, Tran D (2023a) The effects of artificial light at night on behavioral rhythm and
334 related gene expression are wavelength dependent in the oyster *Crassostrea gigas*. *Environ*
335 *Sci Pollut R* 30:120375–120386. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-30793-1>
- 336 Botté A, Payton L, Lefeuvre E, Tran D (2023b) Is part-night lighting a suitable mitigation strategy
337 to limit Artificial Light at Night effects on the biological rhythm at the behavioral and
338 molecular scales of the oyster *Crassostrea gigas*? *Sci Total Environ* 905:167052.
339 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.167052>
- 340 Botté A, Payton L, Tran D (2023c) Artificial light at night at environmental intensities disrupts
341 daily rhythm of the oyster *Crassostrea gigas*. *Mar Pollut Bull* 191:114850.
342 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.114850>
- 343 Bulla M, Oudman T, Bijleveld AI, Piersma T, Kyriacou, Charalambos P (2017) Marine biorhythms:
344 bridging chronobiology and ecology. *Philos T R Soc B* 372:20160253.
345 <http://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2016.0253>
- 346 Bulleri F (2009) Facilitation research in marine systems: state of the art, emerging patterns and
347 insights for future developments. *J Ecol* 97:1121–1130. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365->
348 2745.2009.01567.x
- 349 Bulleri F, Chapman MG (2004) Intertidal assemblages on artificial and natural habitats in marinas
350 on the north-west coast of Italy. *Mar Biol* 145:381-391 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-004->
351 1316-8
- 352 Bulleri F, Chapman MG (2010) The introduction of coastal infrastructure as a driver of change in

353 marine environments. *J Applied Ecol* 47:26–35. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365->
354 2664.2009.01751.x

355 Bullough K, Gaston KJ, Troscianko J (2023) Artificial light at night causes conflicting behavioural
356 and morphological defence responses in a marine isopod. *P R Soc B* 290:20230725.
357 <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2023.0725>

358 Cacabelos E, Martins GM, Thompson R, Prestes ACL, Azevedo JMN, Neto AI (2016) Material
359 type and roughness influence structure of inter-tidal communities on coastal defenses. *Mar*
360 *Ecol* 37:801–812. <https://doi.org/10.1111/maec.12354>

361 Caley A, Marzinelli EM, Byrne M, Mayer-Pinto M (2024) Artificial light at night and warming
362 impact grazing rates and gonad index of the sea urchin *Centrostephanus rodgersii*. *P R Soc*
363 *B* 291:20240415. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2024.0415>

364 Chapman M (2003) Paucity of mobile species on constructed seawalls: effects of urbanization on
365 biodiversity. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 264:21–29. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps264021>

366 Christoforou E, Dominoni D, Lindström J, Diamantopoulou C, Czyzewski J, Mirzai N, Spatharis S
367 (2023) The effects of artificial light at night (ALAN) on the gaping activity and feeding of
368 mussels. *Mar Pollut Bull* 192:115105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.115105>

369 Cianchetti-Benedetti M, Becciu P, Massa B, Dell’Omo G (2018) Conflicts between touristic
370 recreational activities and breeding shearwaters: short-term effect of artificial light and
371 sound on chick weight. *Eur J Wildlife Res* 64:19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10344-018-1178->
372 x

373 Connell SD (2000) Floating pontoons create novel habitats for subtidal epibiota. *J Exp Mar Biol*
374 *Ecol* 247:183–194. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0981\(00\)00147-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0981(00)00147-7)

375 Dalle Carbonare L, Basile A, Rindi L, Bulleri F, Hamedeh H, Iacopino S, Shukla V, Weits DA,
376 Lombardi L, Sbrana A, Benedetti-Cecchi L, Giuntoli B, Licausi F, Maggi E (2023) Dim
377 artificial light at night alters gene expression rhythms and growth in a key seagrass species
378 (*Posidonia oceanica*). *Sci Rep* 13:10620. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-37261-3>

379 Davies TW, Duffy JP, Bennie J, Gaston KJ (2014) The nature, extent, and ecological implications
380 of marine light pollution. *Front Ecol Environ* 12:347–355. <https://doi.org/10.1890/130281>

- 381 Davies TW, Coleman M, Griffith KM, Jenkins SR (2015) Night-time lighting alters the
382 composition of marine epifaunal communities. *Biol Letters* 11:20150080.
383 <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2015.0080>
- 384 Davies TW, Smyth T (2018) Why artificial light at night should be a focus for global change
385 research in the 21st century. *Glob Change Biol* 24:872-882.
386 <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13927>
- 387 Davies TW, Levy O, Tidau S, De Barros Marangoni LF, Wiedenmann J, D'Angelo C, Smyth T
388 (2023) Global disruption of coral broadcast spawning associated with artificial light at night.
389 *Nat Commun* 14:2511. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-38070-y>
- 390 Davis J, Levin L, Walther S (2002) Artificial armored shorelines: sites for open-coast species in a
391 southern California bay. *Mar Biol* 140:1249–1262. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-002-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-002-0779-8)
392 [0779-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-002-0779-8)
- 393 Fobert EK, Burke Da Silva K, Swearer SE (2019) Artificial light at night causes reproductive
394 failure in clownfish. *Biol Letters* 15:20190272. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2019.0272>
- 395 Fobert EK, Schubert KP, Burke Da Silva K (2021) The influence of spectral composition of
396 artificial light at night on clownfish reproductive success. *J Exp Mar Biol Ecol*
397 540:151559. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2021.151559>
- 398 Fogg LG, Cortesi F, Gache C, Lecchini D, Marshall NJ, De Busserolles F (2023) Developing and
399 adult reef fish show rapid light-induced plasticity in their visual system. *Mol Ecol* 32:167–
400 181. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.16744>
- 401 Gao X, Zhang M, Luo Q, Lin S, Lyu M, Ke C (2024) Persistent exposure to artificial light at night
402 (ALAN) accelerates metamorphosis and colonization in larvae of marine shellfish. *Ecol*
403 *Indic* 158:111472. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2023.111472>
- 404 Gaston KJ, Bennie J, Davies TW, Hopkins J (2013) The ecological impacts of nighttime light
405 pollution: a mechanistic appraisal. *Biol Rev* 88:912–927. <https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12036>
- 406 Gaston KJ, Ackermann S, Bennie J, Cox DTC, Phillips BB, Sánchez de Miguel A, Sanders D
407 (2021) Pervasiveness of biological impacts of Artificial Light at Night. *Integr Comp Biol*
408 61:1098–1110. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icb/icab145>

- 409 Georgiadis M, Mavraki N, Koutsikopoulos C, Tzanatos E (2014) Spatio-temporal dynamics and
410 management implications of the nightly appearance of *Boops boops* (*Acanthopterygii*,
411 *Perciformes*) juvenile shoals in the anthropogenically modified Mediterranean littoral zone.
412 *Hydrobiologia* 734:81–96. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-014-1871-z>
- 413 Georgiou D, Reeves SE, Burke Da Silva K, Fobert EK (2024) Artificial light at night impacts night-
414 time activity but not day-time behaviour in a diurnal coral reef fish. *Basic Appl Ecol* 74:74–
415 82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.baae.2023.11.009>
- 416 Gosselin L, Chia F (1995) Distribution and dispersal of early juvenile snails: effectiveness of
417 intertidal microhabitats as refuges and food sources. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 128:213–223.
418 <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps128213>
- 419 Henseler C, Nordström MC, Törnroos A, Snickars M, Pecuchet L, Lindegren M, Bonsdorff E
420 (2019) Coastal habitats and their importance for the diversity of benthic communities: A
421 species- and trait-based approach. *Estuar Coast Shelf S* 226:106272.
422 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2019.106272>
- 423 Hillyer KE, Beale DJ, Shima JS (2021) Artificial light at night interacts with predatory threat to
424 alter reef fish metabolite profiles. *Sci Total Environ* 769:144482.
425 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144482>
- 426 Jechow A, Kyba CCM, Hölker F (2020) Mapping the brightness and color of urban to rural
427 skyglow with all-sky photometry. *J Quant Spectrosc Ra* 250:106988.
428 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jqsrt.2020.106988>
- 429 Kaniewska P, Alon S, Karako-Lampert S, Hoegh-Guldberg O, Levy O (2015) Signaling cascades
430 and the importance of moonlight in coral broadcast mass spawning. *eLife* 4:e09991.
431 <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.09991>
- 432 Klein J, Verlaque M (2008) The *Caulerpa racemosa* invasion: A critical review. *Mar Pollut Bull*
433 56:205–225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2007.09.043>
- 434 Komyakova V, Jaffrés JBD, Strain EMA, Cullen-Knox C, Fudge M, Langhamer O, Bender A,
435 Yaakub SM, Wilson E, Allan BJM, Sella I, Haward M (2022) Conceptualisation of multiple
436 impacts interacting in the marine environment using marine infrastructure as an example.
437 *Sci Tot Environ* 830:154748. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.154748>

- 438 Kramer N, Tamir R, Galindo-Martínez CT, Wangpraseurt D, Loya Y (2023) Light pollution alters
439 the skeletal morphology of coral juveniles and impairs their light capture capacity. *Mar*
440 *Pollut Bull* 193:115212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.115212>
- 441 Leroux P (2014) Surface roughness of concrete with 3D profilometry. Technical Report,
442 NANOVEA. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2771.8561>
- 443 Levy O, Fernandes De Barros Marangoni L, I. C. Benichou J, Rottier C, Béraud E, Grover R,
444 Ferrier-Pagès C (2020) Artificial light at night (ALAN) alters the physiology and
445 biochemistry of symbiotic reef building corals. *Environ Pollut* 266:114987.
446 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.114987>
- 447 Lynn KD, Tummon Flynn P, Manríquez K, Manríquez PH, Pulgar J, Duarte C, Quijón PA (2021)
448 Artificial light at night alters the settlement of acorn barnacles on a man-made habitat in
449 Atlantic Canada. *Mar Pollut Bull* 163:111928.
450 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2020.111928>
- 451 Lynn KD, Quintanilla-Ahumada D, Duarte C, Quijón PA (2024) Artificial light at night alters the
452 feeding activity and two molecular indicators in the plumose sea anemone *Metridium senile*
453 (L.). *Mar Pollut Bull* 202:116352. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2024.116352>
- 454 Maggi E, Benedetti-Cecchi L (2018) Trophic compensation stabilizes marine primary producers
455 exposed to artificial light at night. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 606:1–5.
456 <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps12769>
- 457 Maggi E, Bongiorno L, Fontanini D, Capocchi A, Dal Bello M, Giacomelli A, Benedetti-Cecchi L
458 (2020a) Artificial light at night erases positive interactions across trophic levels. *Funct Ecol*
459 34:694–706. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.13485>
- 460 Maggi E, Bertocci I, Benedetti-Cecchi L (2020b) Light pollution enhances temporal variability of
461 photosynthetic activity in mature and developing biofilm. *Hydrobiologia* 847:1793–1802.
462 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-019-04102-2>
- 463 Manríquez PH, Jara ME, Diaz MI, Quijón PA, Widdicombe S, Pulgar J, Manríquez K, Quintanilla-
464 Ahumada D, Duarte C (2019) Artificial light pollution influences behavioral and
465 physiological traits in a keystone predator species, *Concholepas concholepas*. *Sci Total*
466 *Environ* 661:543–552. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.01.157>

- 467 Manríquez PH, Jara ME, González CP, Seguel M, Quijón PA, Widdicombe S, Pulgar JM,
468 Quintanilla-Ahumada D, Anguita C, Duarte C (2021a) Effects of artificial light at night and
469 predator cues on foraging and predator avoidance in the keystone inshore mollusc
470 *Concholepas concholepas*. Environ Pollut 280:116895.
471 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.116895>
- 472 Manríquez K, Quijón PA, Manríquez PH, Miranda C, Pulgar J, Quintanilla-Ahumada D, Duarte C
473 (2021b) Artificial Light at Night (ALAN) negatively affects the settlement success of two
474 prominent intertidal barnacles in the southeast Pacific. Mar Pollut Bull 168:112416.
475 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2021.112416>
- 476 Marangoni LFB, Davies T, Smyth T, Rodríguez A, Hamann M, Duarte C, Pendoley K, Berge J,
477 Maggi E, Levy O (2022) Impacts of artificial light at night in marine ecosystems—A
478 review. Glob Change Biol 28:5346–5367. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16264>
- 479 Marchesan M, Spoto M, Verginella L, Ferrero EA (2005) Behavioural effects of artificial light on
480 fish species of commercial interest. Fish Res 73:171–185.
481 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2004.12.009>
- 482 Mardones ML, Lambert J, Wiedenmann J, Davies TW, Levy O, D'Angelo C (2023) Artificial light
483 at night (ALAN) disrupts behavioural patterns of reef corals. Mar Pollut Bull 194:115365.
484 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.115365>
- 485 Mavraki N, Georgiadis M, Koutsikopoulos C, Tzanatos E (2016) Unravelling the nocturnal
486 appearance of bogue *Boops boops* shoals in the anthropogenically modified shallow littoral.
487 J Fish Biol 88:2060–2066. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfb.12942>
- 488 Mayer-Pinto M, Cole VJ, Johnston EL, Bugnot A, Hurst H, Airoidi L, Glasby TM, Dafforn KA
489 (2018) Functional and structural responses to marine urbanisation. Environ Res Lett
490 13:014009. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aa98a5>
- 491 McMahon O, Smyth T, Davies TW (2022) Broad spectrum artificial light at night increases the
492 conspicuousness of camouflaged prey. J Appl Ecol 59:1324–1333.
493 <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14146>
- 494 Momota K, Hosokawa S (2021) Potential impacts of marine urbanization on benthic macrofaunal
495 diversity. Sci Rep - UK 11:4028. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-83597-z>

- 496 Moyse E, Firth LB, Smyth T, Tidau S, Davies TW (2023) Artificial light at night alters predation on
497 colour-polymorphic camouflaged prey. *Basic Appl Ecol* 73:88–93.
498 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.baae.2023.11.002>
- 499 O'Connor JJ, Fobert EK, Besson M, Jacob H, Lecchini D (2019) Live fast, die young: Behavioural
500 and physiological impacts of light pollution on a marine fish during larval recruitment. *Mar*
501 *Pollut Bull* 146:908–914. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2019.05.038>
- 502 Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, Shamseer L, Tetzlaff
503 JM, Akl EA, Brennan SE, Chou R, Glanville J, Grimshaw JM, Hróbjartsson A, Lalu MM,
504 Li T, Loder EW, Mayo-Wilson E, McDonald S, McGuinness LA, Stewart LA, Thomas J,
505 Tricco AC, Welch VA, Whiting P, Moher D (2021) The PRISMA 2020 statement: an
506 updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 372:n71.
507 <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>
- 508 Pardal-Souza AL, Dias GM, Jenkins SR, Ciotti AM, Christofolletti RA (2016) Shading impacts by
509 coastal infrastructure on biological communities from subtropical rocky shores. *J Appl Ecol*
510 54(3):826–835. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12811>
- 511 Pulgar J, Zeballos D, Vargas J, Aldana M, Manríquez PH, Manríquez K, Quijón PA, Widdicombe
512 S, Anguita C, Quintanilla D, Duarte C (2019) Endogenous cycles, activity patterns and
513 energy expenditure of an intertidal fish is modified by artificial light pollution at night
514 (ALAN). *Environ Pollut* 244:361–366. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2018.10.063>
- 515 Pulgar J, Manríquez PH, Widdicombe S, García-Huidobro R, Quijón PA, Carter M, Aldana M,
516 Quintanilla-Ahumada D, Duarte C (2023) Artificial Light at Night (ALAN) causes size-
517 dependent effects on intertidal fish decision-making. *Mar Pollut Bull* 193:115190.
518 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.115190>
- 519 Reimann L, Vafeidis AT, Honsel LE (2023) Population development as a driver of coastal risk:
520 Current trends and future pathways. *Camb Prism Coast Futures* 1:e14.
521 <https://doi.org/10.1017/cft.2023.3>
- 522 Rosenberg Y, Doniger T, Levy O (2019) Sustainability of coral reefs are affected by ecological
523 light pollution in the Gulf of Aqaba/Eilat. *Commun Biol* 2:289.
524 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-019-0548-6>

- 525 Schligler J, Cortese D, Beldade R, Swearer SE, Mills SC (2021) Long-term exposure to artificial
526 light at night in the wild decreases survival and growth of a coral reef fish. P R Soc B
527 288:20210454. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2021.0454>
- 528 Slagel S, Lohr K, O'Neil K, Patterson J (2021) Growth, calcification, and photobiology of the
529 threatened coral *Acropora cervicornis* in natural versus artificial light. Zoobiology 40:201–
530 207. <https://doi.org/10.1002/zoo.21589>
- 531 Smyth TJ, Wright AE, Edwards-Jones A, McKee D, Queirós A, Rendon O, Tidau S, Davies TW
532 (2022) Disruption of marine habitats by artificial light at night from global coastal
533 megacities. Elementa: Science of the Anthropocene 10:00042.
534 <https://doi.org/10.1525/elementa.2022.00042>
- 535 Stanton DL, Cowart JR (2024) The effects of artificial light at night (ALAN) on the circadian
536 biology of marine animals. Frontiers in Marine Science 11:1372889.
537 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2024.1372889>
- 538 Steell SC, Cooke SJ, Eliason EJ (2020) Artificial light at night does not alter heart rate or locomotor
539 behaviour in Caribbean spiny lobster (*Panulirus argus*): insights into light pollution and
540 physiological disturbance using biologgers. Conserv Physiol 8:coaa097.
541 <https://doi.org/10.1093/conphys/coaa097>
- 542 Tamir R, Eyal G, Cohen I, Loya Y (2020) Effects of light pollution on the early life stages of the
543 most abundant Northern Red Sea Coral. Microorganisms 8:193.
544 <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8020193>
- 545 Tidau S, Smyth T, McKee D, Wiedenmann J, D'Angelo C, Wilcockson D, Ellison A, Grimmer AJ,
546 Jenkins SR, Widdicombe S, Queirós AM, Talbot E, Wright A, Davies TW (2021) Marine
547 artificial light at night: An empirical and technical guide. Methods Ecol Evol 12:1588–1601.
548 <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13653>
- 549 Tidau S, Whittle J, Jenkins SR, Davies TW (2022) Artificial light at night reverses monthly
550 foraging pattern under simulated moonlight. Biol Letters 18:20220110.
551 <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2022.0110>
- 552 Tidau S, Brough FT, Gimenez L, Jenkins SR, Davies TW (2023) Impacts of artificial light at night
553 on the early life history of two ecosystem engineers. Philos T R Soc B 378:20220363.

- 554 <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2022.0363>
- 555 Trethewy M, Mayer-Pinto M, Dafforn KA (2023) Urban shading and artificial light at night alter
556 natural light regimes and affect marine intertidal assemblages. *Mar Pollut Bull* 193:115203.
557 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.115203>
- 558 Underwood CN, Davies TW, Queirós AM (2017) Artificial light at night alters trophic interactions
559 of intertidal invertebrates. *J Anim Ecol* 86:781–789. [https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-](https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.12670)
560 [2656.12670](https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.12670)
- 561 Vaselli S, Bertocci I, Maggi E, Benedetti-Cecchi L (2008) Effects of mean intensity and temporal
562 variance of sediment scouring events on assemblages of rocky shores. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser*
563 364:57–66. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps07469>
- 564 Wehkamp S, Fischer P (2013) The impact of coastal defence structures (tetrapods) on decapod
565 crustaceans in the southern North Sea. *Mar Environ Res* 92:52–60.
566 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2013.08.011>
- 567 Weiss CM (1947) The effect of illumination and stage of tide on the attachment of barnacle cyprids.
568 *Biol Bull* 93:240–249. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1537972>
- 569 Xu X, Wang Z, Jin X, Ding K, Yang J, Wang T (2023) Effects of Artificial Light at Night on
570 fitness-related traits of sea urchin (*Heliocidaris crassispina*). *Animals* 13:3035.
571 <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani13193035>
- 572 Yoon H-S, Park C-W, Moon S-Y, Han K-H, Suh H-L, An Y-K, Choi S-D (2008) Comparative
573 stomach contents and growth of the juvenile black rockfish *Sebastes inermis* reared in
574 illuminated and unilluminated cages. *Fish Sci* 74:657–661. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1444-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1444-2906.2008.01571.x)
575 [2906.2008.01571.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1444-2906.2008.01571.x)
- 576 Žák P, Vondráčková S (2016) Conception of public lighting. In: 2016 IEEE Lighting Conference of
577 the Visegrad Countries (Lumen V4). IEEE, Karpacz, Poland, pp 1–4
- 578 Zhang M, Gao X, Luo Q, Lin S, Lyu M, Luo X, Ke C, You W (2023) Ecological benefits of
579 artificial light at night (ALAN): Accelerating the development and metamorphosis of marine
580 shellfish larvae. *Sci Total Environ* 903:166683.
581 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.166683>

582 Zhang M, Gao X, Luo Q, Lin S, Lyu M, Luo X, Ke C, You W (2024) Risk assessment of persistent
 583 exposure to artificial light at night revealed altered behavior and metabolic patterns of
 584 marine nocturnal shellfish. *Ecol Indic* 160:111807.
 585 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2024.111807>

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587

588 **Fig.1** Flow diagram of the systematic search process and quantitative information about the identified studies
 589 of Artificial Light At Night (ALAN) effects on hard-bottom habitats. Adapted from the flow diagram
 590 proposed by Page et al. (2021).

592

593 **Fig.2** Light/shadow mosaics generated by the interaction of artificial lighting and different habitat types. **a**
 594 Homogeneously lit area on vertical seawalls. **b** Persistent and/or transient shading by docks and moored
 595 boats (with or without underwater lighting). **c** Regular light/shadow pattern in rip-rap breakwaters. **d**
 596 Heterogeneous distribution of lit and shaded areas in natural rocky shores.